

Synthesis and Spectral Studies of some Novel Thiobenzimidazole, Thiopurine and Thiopyrimidine Derivatives

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Previously, we described the synthesis of substituted diaryl, aryl benzyl sulphides and their corresponding sulphones and sulphoxides, phenylthio acetate and propionate¹. 4-[(4'-Substituted-phenylthio)methyl]-3-nitrobenzoic acids, their sulphinyl and sulphonyl derivatives showed a certain toxicity towards the mosquito larvae². Furthermore, some of them were also found to be effective against bacteria as well as being nontoxic to the tested crops (e.g. wheat). These facts generated our interest in introducing other substituents into the same basic structure but with benzimidazole, purine and pyrimidine nuclei instead of the substituted phenyl group for studying their chemical and biological properties.

Benzimidazoles, purines and pyrimidines nucleosides possess diverse chemotherapeutic potencies³.

A new series of 2'-thiobenzimidazol, 2'-amino-6'-thiopurine and 2'-thiopyrimidine with 4-chloromethylbenzoic acid (1a-c), 4-chloromethyl-3-nitrobenzoic acid (2a-c), 3-chloromethylbenzoic acid (3a-c), their corresponding ethyl esters (4a-c, 5a-c, 6a-c) have been synthesised. Moreover, their reactions with 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene (7a-c), 2,4,6-trinitrochlorobenzene (8a-c) and 2-chloro-5-nitropyridine (9a-c) have also been successfully accomplished. In this respect, the synthetic routes are almost the same as cited in literature. IR spectra of the sulphides showed the expected bands⁴.

(a)

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|------------------------|
| 1; R ₁ = H, | R ₂ = H, |
| 2; R ₁ = NO ₂ , | R ₂ = H, |
| 3; R ₁ = H, | R ₂ = COOH, |
| 4; R ₁ = H, | R ₂ = H, |
| 5; R ₁ = NO ₂ , | R ₂ = H, |

(b)

- | |
|-------------------------|
| R ₃ = COOH, |
| R ₃ = COOH, |
| R ₃ = H, |
| R ₃ = COOEt, |
| R ₃ = COOEt, |

(c)

- | |
|--------------------|
| R ₄ = H |

(7,8a)

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|-------------------------|
| 6; R ₁ = H, | R ₂ = COOEt, |
| 7; R ₁ = NO ₂ , | R ₂ = H, |

(7,8b)

- | |
|------------------------------------|
| R ₃ = H, |
| R ₃ = NO ₂ , |

(7,8c)

- | |
|--------------------|
| R ₄ = H |
| R ₄ = H |

(9a)

(9b)

(9c)

Experimental

M.ps. were determined on a Thoms-Hoover apparatus and are uncorrected, ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra (acetone- d_6 /DMSO- d_6) were recorded on a Varian XL 300 spectrometer with Me_4Si as internal standard, ir spectra (KBr/nujol) on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Shimadzu 160-A spectrophotometer. Tlc were carried out on silica gel using petroleum ether : ethyl acetate (9 : 1). Elemental analyses were carried out in the Faculty of Science, Cairo University. The analyses for C, H, N and S were found satisfactory.

General procedure for the synthesis : A mixture of the chloromethyl benzoic acids or their ethyl esters or chloronitrobenzene or chloronitropyridine (0.1 mol) in ethanol and the sodium salt of the thiol compounds (Aldrich) (0.1 mol) in ethanol was refluxed for 2–3 h. Cooling, dilution and acidification with aqueous HCl gave a solid which was purified by crystallisation.

4-[(2'-Thiobenzimidazol)methyl]benzoic acid (1a) : It was a white solid (88%), m.p. 240–41° (EtOH/H₂O); λ_{max} (dioxane) 240 ($\epsilon = 24\ 990$), $\lambda = 291\ \text{nm}$ (20 320); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 016 (NH), 2 833 (OH), 1 702 (CO), 718 cm^{-1} (C–S); ^1H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6) 4.50 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.41 (2H t, H-5',6'), 7.45 (1H, s, NH), 7.63 (2H, d, H-3,5), 7.68 (2H, d, H-4',7'), 7.88 (2H, d, H-2,6), 11.80 (1H, s, OH); ^{13}C nmr δ_{C} (DMSO- d_6) 35.89 (CH₂), 113.34 (C-5',6'), 124.93 (C-4',7'), 129.73 (C-2,6), 129.16 (C-3,5), 130.33 (C-4), 133.30 (C-1), 141.21 (C-8',9'), 148.99 (C-2'), 166.89 ppm (COOH).

4-[(2'-Amino-6'-thiopurine)methyl]benzoic acid (1b) : It was white solid (72%), m.p. 296–98° (EtOH/H₂O); λ_{max} (dioxane) 241 ($\epsilon = 15\ 250$), 216 nm (13 610); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 457 (NH₂), 3 318 (NH), 2 985 (OH), 1 689 (CO), 737 cm^{-1} (C–S); ^1H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6) 4.52 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.50 (3H, s, NH, NH₂), 7.59 (2H, d, H-3,5), 7.87 (2H, d, H 2,6), 7.92 (1H, s, H-8'), 11.62 (1H, s, OH); ^{13}C nmr δ_{C} (DMSO- d_6) 30.71 (CH₂), 129.22 (C-4',5'), 129.35 (C-3,5), 129.57 (C-2,6), 129.68 (C-4), 129.81 (C-1), 138.50 (C-6') 143.99 (C-8'), 159.59 (C-2'), 167.24 ppm (COOH).

4-[2'-Thiopyrimidine)methyl]benzoic acid (1c) : It was a white solid (83%), m.p. 152–53° (EtOH/H₂O); λ_{max} 252 ($\epsilon = 24\ 990$), 202 nm (19 050); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 916 (OH), 1 703 (CO), 732 (C–S); ^1H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6) 4.25 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.24 (1H, t, H-5'), 7.56 (2H, d, H-3,5), 7.89 (2H, d, H-2,6), 8.66 (2H, d, H-4',6'), 11.42 (1H, s, OH); ^{13}C nmr δ_{C} (DMSO- d_6) 33.98 (CH₂), 116.96 (C-5'), 128.97 (C-4), 129.36 (C-3,5), 129.44 (C-2,6), 143.09 (C-1), 157.81 (C-4'), 163.1 (C-2') 166.99 ppm (COOH).

4-[(2'-Thiobenzimidazol)methyl]-3-nitrobenzoic acid (2a) : It was a pale yellow solid (79%), m.p. 153–54° (EtOH/H₂O), λ_{max} (dioxane) 284 nm ($\epsilon = 15\ 530$); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 056 (NH), 2 814 (OH), 1 682 (CO), 1 525 (NO₂), 748 cm^{-1} (C–S); ^1H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6) 4.50 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.04–7.14 (4H, m, H-4',5',6',7'), 7.40 (1H, s, NH), 7.92 (1H, d, H-5), 8.15 (1H, d, H-6), 8.44 (1H, s, H-2), 12.60 (1H, s, OH); ^{13}C nmr δ_{C} (DMSO- d_6) 31.98 (CH₂), 121.61

(C-4',5',6',7'), 125.44 (C-2), 131.38 (C-4), 132.95 (C-5,6), 133.79 (C-1), 138.04 (C-8',9'), 148.38 (C-3), 148.94 (C-2'), 165.61 ppm (COOH).

4-[(2'-Amino-6'-thiopurine)methyl]-3-nitrobenzoic acid (2b) : It was a yellow solid (78%), m.p. 241–42° (EtOH/H₂O), λ_{max} (dioxane) 219 nm ($\epsilon = 16\ 020$); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 459 (NH₂), 3 075 (NH), 2 995 (OH), 1 639 (CO), 1 518 (NO₂), 779 cm^{-1} (C–S); ^1H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6) 4.90 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.50 (3H, s, NH, NH₂), 7.67 (1H, s, H-8'), 8.07 (d, 1H, H-5), 8.14 (1H, d, H-6), 8.43 (s, 1H, H-2), 12.30 (1H, s, OH), ^{13}C nmr (DMSO- d_6) δ_{C} 28.21 (CH₂), 125.4 (C-2), 129.37 (C-4), 129.82 (C-4',5'), 131.73 (C-5,6), 133.63 (C-1), 138.50 (C-8'), 148.11 (C-3), 159.2 (C-2'), 165.44 ppm (COOH).

4-[(2'-Thiopyrimidine)methyl]-3-nitrobenzoic acid (2c) : It was a pale yellow solid (89%), m.p. 156–68° (EtOH/H₂O); λ_{max} 225 ($\epsilon = 24\ 560$), 243 nm (24 000); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 914 (OH), 1 698 (CO), 1 525 (NO₂), 713 cm^{-1} (C–S); ^1H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6) 4.55 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.25 (1H, t, H-5'), 7.95 (1H, d, H-5), 8.19 (1H, d, H-6), 8.42 (1H, s, H-2), 8.62 (2H, d, H-4',6'), 12.12 (1H, s, OH); ^{13}C nmr δ_{C} (DMSO- d_6) 30.78 (CH₂), 117.75 (C-5'), 125.15 (C-2), 129.47 (C-4), 133.02 (C-5,6), 133.56 (C-1), 138.03 (C-4',6'), 148.03 (C-3), 157.99 (C-2'), 169.70 ppm (COOH).

3-[(2'-Thiobenzimidazol)methyl]benzoic acid (3a) : It was a white solid (87%), m.p. 196–98° (MeOH/H₂O), λ_{max} 284 nm ($\epsilon = 19\ 750$); λ_{max} (KBr) 3 191 (NH), 2 915 (OH), 1 665 (CO), 721 cm^{-1} (C–S); ^1H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6) 4.66 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.10 (2H, t, H-5',6'), 7.25 (2H, d, H-4',7'), 7.35 (1H, s, NH), 7.6–7.8 (3H, m, H-4,5,6), 7.93 (1H, s, H-2), 11.58 (1H, s, OH).

3-[(2'-Amino-6'-thiopurine)methyl]benzoic acid (3b) : It was a white solid (84%), m.p. 285–87°; (DMSO/H₂O), λ_{max} (DMSO) 221 ($\epsilon = 17\ 200$), 277 nm (2 660); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 420 (NH₂), 3 151 (NH), 2 785 (OH), 1 601 (CO), 707 cm^{-1} (C–S); ^1H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6) 4.57 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.27 (3H, s, NH, NH₂), 7.33 (1H, t, H-5), 7.70 (2H, m, H-4,6), 7.80 (1H, s, H-2), 7.93 (1H, s, H-8'), 11.70 (1H, s, OH).

3-[(2'-Thiopyrimidine)methyl]benzoic acid (3c) : It was a white solid (94%), m.p. 162–63° (C₆H₆); λ_{max} (EtOH) 205 ($\epsilon = 20\ 950$), 251 nm (17 400); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 534 (OH), 1 690 (CO), 733 cm^{-1} (C–S); ^1H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6) 4.37 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.87 (1H, t, H-5'), 7.27 (1H, t, H-5), 7.50 (1H, d, H-4), 7.73 (1H, d, H-6), 7.93 (1H, s, H-2), 8.37 (2H, d, H-4',6'), 11.22 (1H, s, OH).

Ethyl 4-[(2'-thiobenzimidazole)methyl]benzoate (4a) : It was a white solid (68%), m.p. 65–67° (EtOH/H₂O); λ_{max} (dioxane) 207 ($\epsilon = 22\ 110$), 236 nm (18 000); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 122 (NH), 1 636 (CO), 752 cm^{-1} (C–S); ^1H nmr δ_{H} (acetone- d_6) 1.31 (3H, t, CH₃ ester), 4.29 (2H, q, CH₂ ester), 4.51 (2H, s, CH₂ benzylic), 7.12–7.17 (4H, m, H-4',5',6',7'), 7.47 (1H, s, NH), 7.61 (2H, d, H-3,5), 7.91 (2H, d, H-2,6); ^{13}C nmr δ_{C} (acetone- d_6) 14.18 (CH₂ ester), 34.68 (CH₂ benzylic), 60.72 (CH₃ ester), 121.49 (C-4',5',6',7'), 128.83 (C-4), 129.18 (C-3,5), 129.31 (C-2,6), 133.58 (C-1),

143.58 (C-8',9'), 149.28 (C-2'), 165.47 ppm (COOR).

Ethyl 4-[(2-amino-6'-thiopurine)methyl]benzoate (4b) : It was a white solid (62%), m.p. 72–74° (EtOH/H₂O); $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 245 ($\epsilon = 24\,990$), 216 (23\,330), 227 nm (19\,070); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3\,464 (NH₂), 3\,215 (NH), 1\,619 (CO), 716 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (acetone-d₆) 1.30 (3H, t, CH₃ ester), 4.38 (2H, q, CH₂ ester), 4.61 (2H, s, CH₂ benzylic), 6.44 (3H, s, NH, NH₂), 7.63 (2H, d, H-3,6), 7.87 (1H, s, H-8'), 7.90 (2H, d, H-2,6); ¹³C nmr δ_{C} (acetone-d₆) 14.17 (CH₂ ester), 30.69 (CH₂ benzylic), 60.69 (CH₃ ester), 128.46 (C-4), 129.15 (C-3,5), 129.54 (C-2,6), 133.21 (C-1), 138.21 (C-6'), 139.14 (C-4',5'), 144.59 (C-8'), 159.56 (C-2'), 165.55 ppm (COOR).

Ethyl 4-[(2'-thiopyrimidine)methyl]benzoate (4c) : It was a white solid (78%), m.p. 59–60° (EtOH/H₂O); $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 247 ($\epsilon = 21\,530$), 217 nm (6\,540); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1\,759 (CO), 714 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (acetone-d₆) 1.30 (3H, t, CH₃ ester), 4.29 (2H, q, CH₂ ester), 4.47 (2H, s, CH₂ benzylic), 7.23 (1H, t, H-5'), 7.57 (2H, d, H-3',5'), 7.89 (2H, d, H-2,8), 8.65 (2H, d, H-4',6'); ¹³C nmr δ_{C} (acetone-d₆) 14.17 (CH₂ ester), 33.73 (CH₂ benzylic), 60.68 (CH₃ ester), 117.55 (C-5), 128.64 (C-4), 129.20 (C-3,5), 129.24 (C-2,6), 133.66 (C-1), 143.66 (C-4',6'), 157.89 (C-2'), 165.49 ppm (COOR).

Ethyl 4-[(2'-thiobenzimidazol)methyl]-3-nitrobenzoate (5a) : It was a pale yellow solid, m.p. 122–24° (EtOH/H₂O); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3\,226 (NH), 1\,705 (CO), 1\,520 (NO₂), 732 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (acetone-d₆) 1.32 (3H, t, CH₃ ester), 4.32 (2H, q, CH₂ ester), 4.48 (2H, s, CH₂ benzylic), 7.18–7.24 (4H, m, H-4',5',6',7'), 7.45 (1H, s, NH), 7.88 (1H, d, H-5), 8.18 (1H, d, H-6), 8.42 (1H, s, H-2); ¹³C nmr δ_{C} (acetone-d₆) 15.12 (CH₂ ester), 31.73 (CH₂ benzylic), 60.18 (CH₃ ester), 119.68 (C-5',6'), 121.22 (C-4',7'), 126.22 (C-2), 128.14 (C-4), 131.92 (C-5,6), 133.79 (C-1), 138.48 (C-8',9'), 148.23 (C-3), 149.13 ppm (C-2').

Ethyl 4-[(2'-amino-6'-thiopurine)methyl]-3-nitrobenzoate (5b) : It was a yellow solid (81%), m.p. >300 (EtOH/H₂O); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3\,450 (NH₂), 3\,178 (NH), 1\,705 (CO), 1\,515 (NO₂), 722 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (acetone-d₆) 1.32 (3H, t, CH₃ ester), 4.30 (2H, q, CH₂ ester), 4.48 (2H, s, CH₂ benzylic), 6.98 (3H, s, NH, NH₂), 7.68 (1H, s, H-8'), 8.10 (1H, d, H-5), 8.18 (1H, d, H-6), 8.38 (1H, s, H-2); ¹³C nmr δ_{C} (acetone-d₆) 14.17 (CH₂ ester), 30.82 (CH₂ benzylic), 60.1 (CH₃ ester), 125.12 (C-2), 128.14 (C-4), 129.12 (C-4',5'), 131.21 (C-5,6), 133.12 (C-1), 138.42 (C-8'), 146.18 (C-3), 157.12 ppm (C-2').

Ethyl 4-[(2'-thiopyrimidine)methyl]-3-nitrobenzoate (5c) : It was a yellow solid (52%) m.p. 212–13° (EtOH/H₂O); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1\,725 (CO), 1\,520 (NO₂), 726 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (acetone-d₆) 1.31 (3H, t, CH₃ ester), 4.28 (2H, q, CH₂ ester), 4.60 (2H, s, CH₂ benzylic), 7.18 (1H, t, H-5'), 7.88 (1H, d, H-5); ¹³C nmr δ_{C} (acetone-d₆) 14.18 (CH₂ ester), 30.78 (CH₂ benzylic), 60.21 (CH₃ ester), 117.85 (C-5'), 125.20 (C-2), 128.78 (C-4), 129.47 (C-5,6), 133.52 (C-1), 138.62 (C-4',6'), 147.52 (C-3), 158.1 ppm (C-2').

Ethyl 3-[(2'-thiobenzimidazol)methyl]benzoate (6a) : It was a white solid (69%), m.p. 70–72° (MeOH); $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 228 ($\epsilon = 17\,600$), 285 nm (17\,530); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3\,129 (NH), 1\,702 (CO), 745 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆) 1.30 (3H, t, CH₃ ester), 4.23 (2H, q, CH₂ ester), 4.46 (2H, s, CH₂ benzylic), 6.46 (1H, s, NH), 7.17 (2H, t, H-5',6'), 7.26–7.52 (3H, m, H-4,5,6), 7.72 (2H, d, H-4',7'), 7.93 (1H, s, H-2).

Ethyl 3-[(2'-amino-6'-thiopurine)methyl]benzoate (6b) : It was a white solid (74%), m.p. 85–86° (MeOH); $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 211 ($\epsilon = 24\,510$), 237 nm (17\,300); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3\,360 (NH₂), 3\,198 (NH), 1\,703 (CO), 732 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆) 1.23 (3H, t, CH₃ ester), 4.18 (2H, q, CH₂ ester), 4.54 (2H, s, CH₂ benzylic), 6.28 (3H, s, NH, NH₂), 7.20 (1H, t, H-5), 7.60 (2H, d, H-4,6), 7.73 (1H, s, H-2), 7.87 (1H, s, H-8').

Ethyl 3-[(2'-thiopyrimidine)methyl]benzoate (6c) : It was a yellow solid (62%), m.p. 157–58° (diethyl ether); $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 207 ($\epsilon = 22\,600$), 236 (20\,800), 248 nm (19\,900); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1\,711 (CO), 685 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆) 1.32 (3H, t, CH₃ ester), 4.25 (2H, q, CH₂ ester), 4.38 (2H, s, CH₂ benzylic), 6.78 (1H, t, H-5'), 7.28 (1H, t, H-5), 7.48 (1H, d, H-4), 7.68 (1H, d, H-6), 8.0 (1H, s, H-2), 8.33 (2H, d, H-4',6').

1-(2'-Thiobenzimidazole)-2,4-dinitrobenzene (7a) : It was a yellow solid (78%), m.p. 120–21° (C₆H₆); $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 264 ($\epsilon = 22\,820$), 232 (16\,650), 213 nm (20\,670); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3\,098 (NH), 1\,526 (NO₂), 736 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆) 5.92 (1H, s, NH), 7.17 (2H, m, H-5',6'), 7.50 (2H, d, H-4',7'), 8.20 (1H, d, H-5), 8.30 (1H, d, H-6), 8.77 (1H, s, H-2).

1-(2'-Amino-6'-thiopurine)-2,4-dinitrobenzene (7b) : It was a yellowish orange solid (73%), m.p. 248° (MeOH); $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 213 ($\epsilon = 21\,430$), 236 (20\,720), 310 nm (13\,470); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3\,315 (NH₂), 3\,090 (NH), 1\,546 (NO₂), 737 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆) 6.33 (3H, s, NH, NH₂), 7.96 (1H, s, H-8'), 8.23 (1H, d, H-5), 8.33 (1H, d, H-6), 8.73 (1H, s, H-2).

1-(2'-Thiopyrimidine)-2,4-dinitrobenzene (7c) : It was a yellow solid (76%), m.p. 62–63° (MeOH); $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 243 ($\epsilon = 14\,280$), 214 (12\,900), 225 nm (12\,330); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1\,553 (NO₂), 721 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆) 7.33 (1H, t, H-5'), 8.33 (1H, d, H-5), 8.50 (1H, d, H-6), 8.60 (2H, d, H-4',6'), 8.75 (1H, s, H-2).

2-(2'-Thiobenzimidazol)-1,3,5-trinitrobenzene (8a) : It was a yellow solid (56%), m.p. $\geq 300^\circ$ (DMF/MeOH); $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 245 ($\epsilon = 50\,600$), 213 (38\,900), 224 nm (24\,500); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3\,097 (NH), 1\,525 (NO₂), 733 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆) 6.45 (1H, s, NH), 7.20 (2H, m, H-5',6'), 7.48 (2H, d, H-4',7'), 8.80 (2H, s, H-2,6).

2-(2'-Amino-6'-thiopurine)-1,3,5-trinitrobenzene (8b) : It was a yellow solid (88%), m.p. 215–17°; $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 240 ($\epsilon = 20\,980$), 212 (19\,420), 417 nm (7\,030); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3\,358 (NH₂), 3\,091 (NH), 1\,528 (NO₂), 731 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆) 6.54 (3H, s, NH, NH₂), 8.40

(1H, s, H-8), 8.87 (2H, s, H-2,6).

2-(2'-Thiopyrimidine)-1,3,5-trinitrobenzene (8c) : It was a white solid (89%), m.p. 115–17° (MeOH); $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 235 ($\epsilon = 21\,240$), 354 nm (3 360); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 557 (NO₂), 793 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆) 7.20 (1H, t, H-5'), 8.47 (2H, d, H-4',6'), 9.00 (2H, s, H-2,6).

2-(2'-Thiobenzimidazol)-5-nitropyridine (9a) : It was a yellow solid (91%), m.p. 180–82° (MeOH); $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 214 ($\epsilon = 15\,980$), 283 (14 230), 323 nm (14 460); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 054 (NH), 1 560 (NO₂), 720 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆) 7.13 (2H, m, H-5',6'), 7.38 (2H, d, H-4',7'), 7.47 (1H, s, NH), 8.27 (1H, d, H-3), 8.36 (1H, d, H-4), 9.10 (1H, s, H-6).

2-(2'-Amino-6'-thiopurine)-5-nitropyridine (9b) : It was a yellow solid (73%), m.p. 240–01° (MeOH/DMF); $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 215 ($\epsilon = 18\,410$), 337 nm (8 100); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 492 (NH₂), 3 176 (NH), 1 559 (NO₂), 747 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆) 6.53 (3H, s, NH, NH₂), 8.10 (1H, s, H-8'), 8.37 (1H, d, H-3), 8.47 (1H, d, H-4), 9.20 (1H, s, H-6).

2-(2'-Thiopyrimidine)-5-nitropyridine (9c) : It was crystallised from MeOH/H₂O as colourless needles (81%), m.p. 173–75°; $\lambda_{\max}$ (dioxane) 213 ($\epsilon = 9\,990$), 244 (13 170), 327 nm (12 280); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 553 (NO₂), 749 cm⁻¹ (C-S), ¹H nmr δ_{H} (DMSO-d₆) 7.27 (1H, t, H-5), 8.10 (1H, d, H-4'), 8.50 (1H, d, H-4), 8.53 (1H, d, H-6'), 9.17 (1H, s, H-6).

References

1. F. M. EL-HEGAZY, A. A. EL-BARDAN and E. A. HAMED, *Phosphorus, Sulfur, Silicon J.*, 1994, **113**, 88, and references cited therein.
2. Y. RIAD, H.M. EL-NAHAS, EL-KADY and A. A. EL-BARDAN, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1992, **85**, 2096; S. R. EL-ZEMITY, M.Sc. Thesis, Alexandria University, 1989.
3. L. DE NAPOLI, L. MAYOL, G. PICCIALLI, M. ROSSO and C. SANTACROSE, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1986, **23**, 140; A. GANGJEE and I. O. DONKOR, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1989, **26**, 705; V. J. RAM, U. K. SINGHA and P.Y. GURU, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1990, **25**, 533; A. GUPTA, SHAIHLA, R. L. MITAL and L. PRAKASH, *Il. Farmaco*, 1992, **47**, 979; N. H. ESHAB, *Alex. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1995, **9**, 31.
4. R. M. SILVERSTEIN, G. C. BASSLER and T. C. MORRILL, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 5th. ed., Wiley New York, 1991.